

Review Article

A Critical Reflection on COVID-19: The Era of Infodemic versus
Truth-Telling in Nigerian Context

Ayo O. Fadahunsi and Adewale, O. Owoseni

¹Department of Psychology, Federal University, Gashua, Yobe, Nigeria.

²Department of Philosophy, University of Ibadan, Ibadan Nigeria.

Corresponding author: a.owoseni@yahoo.com

Abstract

Eni Sàngó bá ti ojú ẹ jà, kò ní báwọ̀n bú Ọba Kòso - He who witnesses the wrath of Sàngó on an offender, would not dare to take Sàngó for granted. The proverbial expression incites the critical mind to remain ever in search of the validity of claims, to attain a supposed reliable ground of justification for dismissing doubts about occurrence of events or happenings. Little wonder that the Yoruba people aptly compares such condition of claim to knowledge with a witness' testimony of the terrible outcome of Sango's thunderous wrath on defaulting offenders, sanctioned to be guilty for something by the investigative cult of Sango. So much for the metaphor! The issue of COVID-19 is yet to be due for invoking the Sango stamp of sanction, which makes it quite a complex issue that demands more than one thousand ways of reflection. The reality of COVID-19 still looms large, accompanied by the much circulated impression from some quarters of such reality as myth or 'politicised' panic devised for the purpose of global economic power shift and hegemony, African nations not exempted. In this paper, we employ rational and critical thinking from the philosophical angle to reflect on how recovery from COVID-19 remains trapped in the circulation of myth, panic and reality within the context of Nigeria. The paper argues that until the value of truth-telling is implicated, anticipated substantial recovery from COVID-19 pandemic would remain plagued by the lingering consequences of infodemic (misinformation).

Keywords: COVID-19, Myth, Panic, Nigeria, Truth-Telling.

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Introduction

Myth, Panic and Reality of COVID-19 in Nigerian Context

The first wave of COVID-19 outbreak began to take its tour on Nigeria sometimes around February, following the *unrestrained* influx of expatriates and citizens from affected diasporic regions of the world into the country (NCDC 2020). Unlike the pro-active health surveillance system put in place in most developed nations of the world to put on hold international boundary movement/transit, the Nigerian government did not appear to have acted quite fast enough to ensure the closure of local and international transit entrances that is airport, seaport and roads. Following the social-media proliferation of the first reported case of the Italian expatriate as a COVID-19 patient on February 27, 2020, who was *rumoured* to have slept in a hotel and had contact with a driver, who was also reported to have transited to Ibadan and Ogun State; the atmosphere within the country became instantly tensed with mixed feelings. These mixed feelings took the form of heightened panic as well as mythical dismissal of the material reality of the pandemic itself as an elite class based phenomenon due to the social status of those reported to be infected.

Panic, rather took a 'classless turn' of circulation on citizenry psyche within the nation on the ground of uncertainty about the number of people who had come in contact with these people of high profile. The stark reality of this precarity due to the unselective nature of the pandemic with daily broadcast on electronic and news media about increase in the number of persons infected aggravate the condition of these mixed feelings to be trapped in the phase of *infodemic* update of confirmed cases, the process or cause of contracting the viral disease, cost of recovery and accessibility, as well as the privilege of care. All these factors culminate into public suspicion about the continuity of political and socio-economic inequality and prioritisation of life among the Nigerian public. A simple point in reference to this would be the unsystematic way of erecting below standard public isolation centres 'armed' with medical and health care givers that are not equipped with sufficient PPE and facilities enough to accommodate those diagnosed with symptomatic or asymptomatic effects of the disease. The intense politics at the global stage involving China, America, and WHO and other nations did little to help this situation (WHO, 2020; Brookings Institution, 2020; NYTimes 2020). It is indeed at this level that the realisation that beyond the epidemiological intricacies of COVID-19, the world and Nigeria among other African nations is being confronted with the lingering consequences of *infodemic*, that is misinformation about the truth value of COVID-19 and its far reaching implications.

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The Chasm of *Infodemic*

While the statistical exhibition of COVID-19 cases around the world can never be considered overrated, the ethical justification of timely and trustworthy information about the situation remains indubitably essential for unsettling the precarity hinted in the preceding section. In manifest reality, the world has witnessed the perpetuation of insufficient and excessive bias of seeking and disseminating information (Hu *et al.* In-Press) through corporate/state owned media houses, online social media outfit and newsprint release about the causal actors (China and the yoke of the conspiracy theory - 5G) of COVID-19, reputation of global super-power states and organisation (USA and the WHO), health care benefits/privileges as well as the undertone of global *gaming* of anti-COVID-19 efforts (as in the case of Madagascar and non-super-power states).

Without mincing words, Nigeria as a nation has its own share of the global *infodemic*. On the one hand is the media broadcast of the increasing numbers of people with COVID-19 across the 36 states of the nation, which is often questioned/doubted by the Nigerian public due to the non-disclosure of how these figures are obtained or determined in the absence of sufficient evidential testing and location of isolation centres where such persons are contained. In some cases, news report on Nigerian television stations corroborate this sceptical suspicion of manipulation of numbers of persons infected with COVID-19 through documentary clips of the supposed persons in ill-equipped centres, who lavish with sumptuous meals and are well maintained. In fact, media reports through daily newspaper release harvest interviews with some persons who narrate that they are being paid to reside in these centres to give credence to the 'truth' of this pandemic. It is difficult to forget easily the case of supposed COVID-19 patients' who escaped from isolation centers in Kano State (Premium Times, 2020) and other parts of the country due to complaint about lack of standardised health care, negligence of health care givers, stigma and so on.

However, the ambivalent nature of this media projection takes another turn with the report of foremost statesmen and public officials who were declared COVID-19 positive, causing the death of a few prominent statesmen. The immediate past SGF and former governor of Oyo State are handful examples here. Another face of the chasm is the poorly disaggregate strategy or mechanism of palliative measures enhanced by the state. Impressions were that the government, in the bid to domesticate the lock down strategy from global arena did not embark on the agenda in truth and sincerity. Allegations that the FG paid much attention to the Northern regions in terms of palliative at the expense of the Southern regions were popular (allAfrica.com 2020). This

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sort of thinking spurred disenchantment of the general citizenry attitude towards the reality of the pandemic outbreak and its far reaching effect of economic stagnancy, anti-social impact and ethnic suspicion.

The oppositional intrigues of the national measures of the lock down strategy, that varies from state to state depending on need or expediency is another angle to the chasm. Oyo state government, for instance, never at any point in time endorsed the national directive of total lock down besides curfew regulations to ease economic condition of the people, since it seems in the state's discretion; total lock down has ripple effect of uneasy survival for people who are not civil servants. This situation of non-uniformity of the national strategy from state to state towards addressing the pandemic reflects the flip side of *infodemic*, especially the case of disenchantment of the populace, in terms of perception about the pandemic as myth or mere politically-driven panic, spurred especially by the overreaching effect on people in the political and elite class. This sort of impression is the basis of the rationale of distrust and lack of confidence exhibited by the Nigerian public about the hard reality of COVID-19 pandemic and its indiscriminate effect on all persons on equal ground. Reality such as this re-enacts the expedient need to embrace the principle of truth-telling as a psycho-socio-economic value in fostering the reliability and validity of information that has to do with the non-negotiable duty/obligation of the state, which is essentially the safety and protection of lives.

Recovery: The Prospect of Truth-Telling

Truth-telling is a conceptual principle that is dominantly utilised in bio-medical related issues that concern the transparency and honesty of releasing information considered crucial for safeguarding human life, as a sacrosanct value (Madhiwalla, 2013; Pickup, 2016; Zolkefli. 2018). Controversial arguments exist regarding the limitation or extent of this principle, but this is not the main point of emphasis here. As earlier noted, the privation of truth-telling leads to distrust, lack of confidence and in extreme ends, indifference and disenchantment. Given the circulated *infodemic* about governmental intention to curb the spread of COVID-19, global conspiracy of actors, class/ethnic suspicion, unequalled health care privileges, as well as inappropriate dependent national strategies; it seems clear that for the average Nigerian public, lack of truth-telling is core to the nature of *infodemic*, which would continually become inscribed in the people's mind-set, even much after some future stride is attained to mitigate the spread of COVID-19.

One essential question still is; how do people recover post-COVID-19 from this lingering consequences of *infodemic*? It remains quite difficult to avoid

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arguing in circle at this point. This is to imply that a plausible way to aid such recovery would be to enshrine the principle of truth-telling within the polity. Another fundamental concern would be; who is to tell the truth? How is the truth to be relayed or actionable? In response to this, the bulk of truth-telling necessarily needs to proceed from the state/government to the citizenry. The sole reason for this is simply because the state represents the investment of citizenry trust and commonwealth, hence it possesses the magnanimous capacity to ensure truth-telling into actionable plans or intention to curb distrust, lack of confidence and suspicion of citizenry in all forms on issues that are crucial to safeguarding lives and good health (in lieu of COVID-19). The government can ensure this by priming itself up in the process of self-inquiry and reflection (Pickup, 2016).

By self-inquiry and reflection, we refer to governmental readiness to uphold its primary duty/obligation to source immediate and relevant solutions to challenges that confront citizenry's commonwealth. In other words, the state needs to turn an indiscriminate searchlight on itself through policy formulation and strategies to ensure equality of health care benefits and privileges, standardised palliative and surveillance schemes to ensure that all these are done. In concrete terms, this may imply the need for **social re-engineering** and **restructuring** by embracing autochthonous approaches to national problems or challenges. After all, there is nothing wrong in enjoining African-based solutions to African-based problems as long as it has a universal benefit for the survival of humanity. Madagascar has taken the lead in this direction, Nigeria needs not resist to follow a similar path as this is a progressive way to stem down the ambivalence of government-citizenry distrust bequeathed by the lingering consequences of *infodemic*, triggered by COVID-19.

Conclusion

In light of the foregoing, the bulk has been passed to the government to take the lead in enhancing truth-telling as a means to recover from the *infodemic* associated with COVID-19 in lieu of post-COVID-19 era. However, this is not to obliterate the citizens of their obligation in terms of compliance to practicable State/ governmental provisional measures to curb the far reaching effect of COVID-19 and *infodemic*. The emphasis in this discourse is that the state must take the lead in this matter. As the Yoruba would say, *agbájoowó la fí n sòyà* – no person is an island on her own, it is only through solidarity and cooperation that we can achieve any feat.

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